

An investigation of the dust load and metal content from an industrial hub (greater Saldanha Bay area and beyond, Western Cape)

Dr. Heleen C. Vos

1 Introduction

Activities around the port and industrial area of Saldanha Bay led to the visible emission and deposition of dust, which has raised concerns about the impact of these particles on public health and the environment. A project initialized in 2022 aimed at understanding the spatial and temporal variation of the dust, the geochemical characteristics of this dust, and the potential environmental impacts of this dust. The results of the work on this project up to 2023 have been summarized in the BIOGRIP Report from February 2024 titled “*An investigation of the potential sources, transport mechanisms, and health impacts of particulate matter and toxic metals in the Saldanha Bay Municipality*”. The 2024 scientific outcomes are presented in more detail in Vos et al. (in prep.) and the Honours theses Kradzandima (2024). This report summarises the results of the efforts and the progress made in 2024 and serves as an addition to the initial BIOGRIP Report 2024.

2 Saldanha Bay

The Saldanha Bay Municipality, located on the west coast of South Africa in the Western Cape Province, hosts the Saldanha Bay port. This is a large port that is responsible for the processing and transport of large quantities of mining material. Associated with this port is the industrial area, where materials are processed and stored and where metals are being produced. In total, the most important products that are being processed include iron ore, manganese ore, steel (including galvanised steel), heavy minerals, and metals such as copper, lead, and zinc (AEC, 2022). Besides the port and industrial area, a number of towns form part of the Saldanha Bay Municipality, from which Saldanha and Vredenburg are the most populated ones. In the southern part of the municipality is the West Coast National Park, which hosts a high biodiversity (Fig 2).

The industrial processes taking place in the Saldanha Bay area have led to the visible emission and deposition of dust (Figure 1). The presence of this dust has resulted in concerns about the impact of the emitted dust on the communities living in the surrounding area. These impacts include the potential negative health impact but also damage to properties and costs associated with cleaning the dust. The visible red dust coming from the iron ore might not be the only aerosol particles associated with industrial activities leading to a negative health impact. Especially smelting activities and manganese ore processing would emit fine, toxic particles. The BIOGRIP project aims to understand the characteristics of the dust and the potential impacts associated with these particles.

Figure 1. The presence of red dust from the iron ore that is being transported and processed at the Saldanha Bay port.

3 Methodology

The methodology used a variation of established and novel techniques for determining the content and quantity of dust particles and followed the same approach as described in the BIOGRIP Report 2024. The differences between the geochemical content and the concentration of dust and a more extensive discussion of the methodology are described in the

3.1 Geochemical monitoring

This project works in close collaboration with the Saldanha Bay Municipality. The Saldanha Bay Municipality established a long-term air quality monitoring programme from 2014 onwards (<https://sbm.gov.za/environmental/>). The Saldanha Bay Municipality has been monitoring the content (in ppm, or parts per million) of iron (Fe), lead (Pb), manganese (Mn), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu) in the dust, and the total dust deposition flux (in $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), following the guidelines of the Air Quality Act (DEA, 2012, 2013). Combining the measured metal content and total dust deposition flux allows the assessment of the metal deposition flux (in $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$). The Municipality has been monitoring seven sampling sites and analysing the dust every month (Figure 2). In addition, this project set up a suite of Big Spring Number Eight samplers (BSNEs), which are passive dust samplers that allow sampling of the horizontal dust flux ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) and measuring the chemical content of the bulk dust. In total, 26 elements were analysed with a particular emphasis on the metals and metalloids (Supplementary 1). Six BSNEs were installed (Figure 2) and were analysed approximately every 2 months (Supplementary 2). The BSNEs were mainly installed on the private property of volunteering citizens to prevent vandalism. A more extensive discussion of the geochemical monitoring by the municipality and using the BSNE sampler has been presented in the BIOGRIP Report 2024. In addition, to determine the chemical content of the dust, a High Volume Air Sampler (HVAS) was installed at the municipality's Industrial Development Zone (IDZ, Figure 2) from the 8th of November 2024 to the 12th of November 2024. The HVAS is an active sampler, meaning it relies on pumping in air to sample dust particles. For the HVAS, the particles will be collected on cellulose Whatman filters. This allows for a higher mass of dust sampled, a more precise assessment of the chemical content of a wide range of dust particle sizes, and minimizing the risk of contamination. The sampling is generally done every 24 hours, making it a more labour-intensive type of sampling.

Figure 2. A map of the Saldanha Bay Municipality, showing the location of the dust bucket stations for monitoring by the Municipality (a) and the location of the BSNE samplers for additional monitoring (b), see also section 3.1.

Figure 3. The BSNE sampler and the dust bucket from the Municipality are shown on the left and right, respectively, at Blouwater Bay (a) and the HVAS (b) at the IDZ.

3.2 PM_{2.5} monitoring

The PM_{2.5} concentration (generally expressed in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) is considered one of the most important markers for the health risks posed by particulate matter (Atkinson et al., 2013; Babatola, 2018; WHO, 2021, 2016). The municipality monitored the PM_{2.5} concentration from 2015 to 2018 but then stopped the monitoring efforts due to the equipment being vandalised. To add recent PM_{2.5} measurements, a PurpleAir sensor has been installed in Vredenburg (Figure 4a). This sensor measured, among others, the PM_{2.5} concentration in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at a 2-minute interval. This sensor broke on the 31st of July 2024 and was replaced on the 12th of November 2024. The effect of PM_{2.5} on public health is a long-term process that shows annual, seasonal, and daily variation (Vos et al. 2023).

In 2024, we started a collaboration with the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering at Stellenbosch University, which is developing its own PM_{2.5} sensors. The first sensor was developed by PhD candidate Rita van der Walt and installed at the Industrial Development Zone (IDZ) on the 26th of September 2024 (Figure 4b). Similarly to the PurpleAir sensor, this sensor measures the PM_{2.5} concentration at a 1-minute interval. At the moment, this setup is expanded with five more sensors that are being developed by PhD candidate Christopher Erasmus. This will allow assessing the PM_{2.5} value at multiple towns in the Municipality and therefore better understanding of the spatial variability of the health impact. It could also help pinpoint possible harmful sources better.

Figure 4. The PurpleAir PM_{2.5} sensor at Vredenburg (a) and the PM_{2.5} sensor made by Stellenbosch University Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering PhD candidate Rita van der Walt at the IDZ (b).

3.3 Data analyses

The analysis of the bulk dust particles collected using the BSNE samplers provides the concentration (in ppm) of 26 elements (Supplementary 1) in the dust particles. To determine the enrichment of the separate elements, the Enrichment Factor (EF) was used. The EF normalises each element to Al and calculates the enrichment of this value to that of the continental crust values (Wedepohl, 1995). Details on these calculations can be found in the BIOGRIP Report 2024. Generally, it is assumed that a high EF value can indicate an anthropogenic origin of the dust (Buck et al., 2019; Reimann and Caritat, 2005).

Meteorological data was obtained using the weather station at Langebaanweg (Figure 1). Hourly wind direction and wind velocity were used to create polar plots. These polar plots allow, in combination with PM_{2.5} data, to visualise the relationship between wind conditions and PM_{2.5}, and support the assessment of the origin of polluting wind conditions. More information on the polar plots is given in the BIOGRIP Report 2024.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Spatial and temporal variation of dust concentration and quantity

As described by Vos et al. (2024), there is a large spatial variation in the dust load throughout the municipality, which appears to be influenced by the proximity to the industrial area, the main wind direction, and the geography of the area. Figure 5 shows the PM_{2.5} measurements in

Vredenburg and the IDZ, as described in section 3.2. The average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration is $6.45 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Vredenburg and $9.76 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the IDZ. The high $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in the IDZ can likely be attributed to the proximity to the industrial activities and port area.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) standard, the current National Ambient Air Quality Standard (NAAQS) and the standard of 2030 are shown in Supplementary 3. Here, especially the exceedance of the daily standards in Vredenburg is relevant, since this is the town with the highest number of residents, whereas the IDZ is an industrial area where fewer people are continuously exposed to the dust. To plot the relationship between the wind direction, wind velocity, and the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration, polar plots of the $PM_{2.5}$ monitoring in Vredenburg and the IDZ were made, see Figure 5. In both areas, high $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations were associated with both low wind speeds, and higher wind speeds from the north to the west (Figure 7). The source of this high concentration has yet to be determined. The moderately high $PM_{2.5}$ concentration coming from the southeast and southwest at Vredenburg and the IDZ, respectively, is likely the iron ore port area. The chemical composition of size-fractionated dust particles could confirm this.

Figure 5. The hourly $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in Vredenburg (a) and the IDZ (b). The black line in both graphs represents the daily average and the gray line represents the maximum daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration as described by the 2030 standards of the NAAQS. The methodology and monitoring periods are described in section 3.2.

Figure 6. Polar plots of the PM_{2.5} measurements in Vredenburg (a) and the IDZ (b) in 2024 showing the relationship between the PM_{2.5} concentration, the wind direction, and the wind velocity. The hourly PM_{2.5} concentration is shown in Figure 5 and the methods and monitoring periods are described in section 3.2.

4.2 Geochemistry of dust

Figure 7 shows the trace metal content and the EF of bulk dust particles collected with the BSNE samplers during the different sampling periods. As discussed in the BIOGRIP Report 2024, there might be contamination of Zn from the sampler, which would explain the high concentration and concentration variability of this element. Analyses of the dust sampled by the HVAS active high-volume sampler can confirm whether this contamination has occurred. Besides Zn, the highest concentrations were observed for Na, Ca, Fe, Al, and Si. However, the EF indicate that these elements are on average only moderately enriched (average EF below 10;

Figure 7). Anthropogenic enrichment (average EF above 10) is indicated for Cu, As, Se, Cd, Sn, and Pb

Figure 7. Furthermore, the concentrations of most elements between areas and sampling periods vary largely. This highlights the importance of long-term dust monitoring in multiple areas to accurately assess the presence, exposure, and risk of heavy metals in dust particles.

Figure 7. Trace metal concentration in bulk dust collected with the BSNE passive samplers (left) and the EF of these values (right) in Blouwater Bay, IDZ, Saldanha, St Helena Bay, and Vredenburg during the different measurements period, whereby period A is from 13-11-2023 till 08-02-2024, B is from 08-02-2024 till 22-04-2024, C is from 22-04-2024 to 25-06-2024, and D is from 25-06-2024 to 30-07-2024 (see also Supplementary 2). The bottom graphs show the average per sampling site from the different sampling periods.

4.3 Potential health risks

The BIOGRIP Report 2024 provided a first risk assessment based on the potentially toxic metals in the dust. This risk assessment includes a model from the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), which relies on the calculation of the Daily Chemical Intake, from which the non-carcinogenic Hazard Index and Carcinogenic Risk can be calculated (US EPA, 2024, 2011, 1996, 1989). Here, a value above 1 for the Hazard Index and a value above 10^{-4} for the Carcinogenic Risks can be considered as a significant risk to human health. The method of

calculation of these values is shown in the BIOGRIP Report 2024. Recent measurements have expanded the health risk assessment by expanding the knowledge of the dust contents (Vos et al., in prep.). The dataset was split between the municipality's long-term monitoring with dust buckets and the monitoring using the additional BSNE samplers (Figure 8). Mn and Pb appear to pose the highest risks (Figure 8). It should be noted that the risk for Fe is below the health risk threshold, and does not pose a significant risk to public health, despite being the most visible component of the dust emitted from the port area (Figure 1). This shows the importance of considering the industrial area and manganese ore processing as a possibly relevant dust source.

Figure 8. Health risk assessment (adapted from Vos et al., in prep.), including the Hazard Index (a and c), which represents the non-carcinogenic risks, and the Carcinogenic Risks (b and d). Data from the municipality's dust bucket monitoring (a and b) and that from the BSNE monitoring (c and d) are shown. The elements marked with an asterisk (*) represent the elements for which certain information required in the Hazard index calculations are not available and hence, best assumptions had to be made, see BIOGRIP Report 2024 for more information.

5 Ongoing and future work

Several developments and measurements related to the BIOGRIP project. These include:

Size fractionated aerosol analyses

For work in 2025, active dust sampling using the HVAS will be continued. This sampling will include the use of a cascade impactor, a sampling device that captures particles of different size classes on different filters. This will allow determining in which classes the toxic particles occur, whereby smaller particles are considered more harmful. Size fractionated measurements could

link the real-time sensor and snapshot sampler data. This will also allow addressing to what extent the current passive sampling with the BSNE and dust buckets represents the full range of dust particles, and if certain errors due to the methodology need to be taken into account.

Develop extensive PM_{2.5} network

The ongoing collaboration with the Stellenbosch University Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering will lead to the development of five extra PM_{2.5} sensors. This way, multiple residential and industrial areas can be monitored. As previously mentioned by Vos et al. (2024), there is a high spatial and temporal diversity in the air pollution in this area, and expanding the PM_{2.5} monitoring allows for increasing the confidence of the data produced.

Soil measurements

In 2025 we will do a high spatial sampling of the soils in the Saldanha Bay municipality. This way, the effects of industrial activities on the local environment can be addressed. It will also contribute to the knowledge of any highly-polluted areas and sources.

Bioavailability

The health index and the carcinogenic risk index calculations require an assessment of bioavailability in the human body. Bioavailability is a crucial parameter for estimating the health risks that dust particles pose (Drahota et al., 2018; Kastury et al., 2017; Zheng et al., 2020). Lastly, it is an important indicator of the fertilizing and damaging effects in oceanic environments (Ito and Shi, 2016; Li et al., 2017; Myriokefalitakis et al., 2016). In 2025, dust particles sampled from the HVAS will be analysed on their bioavailability to contribute to the issues.

Analyses of the microbial community in the dust

A new collaboration with Dr. Nonsikelelo Hlongwa from the African MicroBiome research group from the Department of Microbiology of Stellenbosch University explores dust sampling in parallel with geochemical analyses and microorganism analyses. These measurements rely on the SASS3100 Dry Air Samplers, Whatman-41 cellulose filters, and HEPA-Style electret filters (Figure 9). The measurements and analyses are ongoing and will be done in multiple areas, including the Saldanha Bay Municipality. Measurements on the microbial community associated with the dust particles in industrial areas would be innovative work and shine a light on a very understudied aspect of the harmful aspects of air pollution.

Figure 9. The SASS3100 Dry Air Sampler with a Whatman 41 filter (a) and two of these sampler installed on campus at Stellenbosch University (b).

6 Additional information

6.1 Publications and reports

In 2024, one manuscript has been accepted for publication in the journal *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health* and one is in preparation. Furthermore, a contribution was made to the State of the Atmosphere report, which summarises the scientific findings on air pollution in the Saldanha Bay Municipality. Lastly, an Honours thesis was produced with the data shown in this report. The details of the manuscripts are summarised below:

- Vos, H.C., Kanguuehi, K.I., Toesie, R., Eckardt, F.D., Ravenscroft, G., Fietz, S., 2024. Spatial variability of dust concentration and deposition around an industrial port in South Africa emphasises the complexity of sources and transport. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-024-01581-8>
- Vos, H.C., Kanguuehi, K.I., Toesie, R., Ravenscroft, G., Fietz, S., 2024. Health risks of the potentially toxic metals in dust around an industrial hub. In prep.
- Karadzandima A. The Potential Biomedical Effects of Dust in Saldanha Bay. BSc Honours thesis, Department of Earth Sciences, Stellenbosch University.
- State of the Atmosphere Report. In development

6.2 Students involved

Students involved in the project and who were supervised for their thesis:

- Karadzandima A. The Potential Biomedical Effects of Dust in Saldanha Bay. BSc Honours thesis, Department of Earth Sciences, Stellenbosch University.
- Gaoaaga, K. Geochemical Characterisation and Morphology of Fine Inhalable Particles (PM_{2.5}) In Residential Areas of the Western Cape, South Africa, MSc thesis, Department of Earth Sciences, Stellenbosch University.

6.3 Conferences visited

National Association for Clean Air, 55th Annual Conference, Johannesburg, 4 -6th of September

- 3 Minute Research Talk: Health Risks of the Potentially Toxic Metals in Dust around the Industrial Hub of Saldanha Bay
- Poster Presentation: Spatial and Temporal Variation of Potentially Toxic Metals in Dust around the Industrial Hub of Saldanha Bay
- Poster Presentation: The Potential Biomedical Effects of Dust in Saldanha Bay
- Poster Presentation: Geochemical characterisation and morphology of fine inhalable particles (PM₁₀) in residential areas of the Western Cape, South Africa

6.4 Stakeholders

This project was done in collaboration with the following stakeholders at the Saldanha Bay Municipality:

- Ms. René Toesie
 - Senior Manager: Support Services (Infrastructure Planning Services)
 - +27(0) 22 701 7052
 - Rene.toesie@sbm.gov.za
 - www.sbm.gov.za

7 References

- AEC, 2022. The State of Saldanha Bay and Langebaan Lagoon 2021/2022 (Technical Report September 2022). Anchor Environmental Consultants, Cape Town.
- Atkinson, R., Barregård, L., Bellander, T., Burnett, R., Cassee, F., Fernandes, E.D.O., Forastiere, F., Forsberg, B., Wothe (Henschel), S., Hoek, G., Holgate, S., Janssen, N., Jantunen, M., Kelly, F., Lanki, T., Mills, I., Mudway, I., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., Ostro, B., Williams, M., 2013. Review of evidence on health aspects of air pollution – REVIHAAP Project Technical Report.
- Babatola, S.S., 2018. Global burden of diseases attributable to air pollution. *Journal of public health in Africa* 9.
- Buck, C.S., Aguilar-Islas, A., Marsay, C., Kadko, D., Landing, W.M., 2019. Trace element concentrations, elemental ratios, and enrichment factors observed in aerosol samples collected during the US GEOTRACES eastern Pacific Ocean transect (GP16). *Chemical Geology* 511, 212–224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2019.01.002>
- DEA, 2013. National Environmental Management: Air Quality Act, 2004. Department Of Environmental Affairs.
- DEA, 2012. National Ambient Air Quality Standard For Particulate Matter With Aerodynamic Diameter Less Than 2.5 Micron Metres (PM_{2.5}). Department of Environmental Affairs (DEA).
- Drahota, P., Raus, K., Rychlíková, E., Rohovec, J., 2018. Bioaccessibility of As, Cu, Pb, and Zn in mine waste, urban soil, and road dust in the historical mining village of Kaňk, Czech Republic. *Environmental Geochemistry and Health* 40, 1495–1512. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-017-9999-1>
- Ito, A., Shi, Z., 2016. Delivery of anthropogenic bioavailable iron from mineral dust and combustion aerosols to the ocean. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 16, 85–99.
- Kangueehi, K.I., 2021. Southern African dust characteristics and potential impacts on the surrounding oceans (PhD Thesis). Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University.
- Kastury, F., Smith, E., Juhasz, A.L., 2017. A critical review of approaches and limitations of inhalation bioavailability and bioaccessibility of metal(loid)s from ambient particulate matter or dust. *Science of The Total Environment* 574, 1054–1074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.09.056>
- Li, W., Xu, L., Liu, X., Zhang, J., Lin, Y., Yao, X., Gao, H., Zhang, D., Chen, J., Wang, W., others, 2017. Air pollution–aerosol interactions produce more bioavailable iron for ocean ecosystems. *Science advances* 3, e1601749.
- Myriokefalitakis, S., Nenes, A., Baker, A.R., Mihalopoulos, N., Kanakidou, M., 2016. Bioavailable atmospheric phosphorous supply to the global ocean: a 3-D global modeling study. *Biogeosciences* 13, 6519–6543.
- Reimann, C., Caritat, P. de, 2005. Distinguishing between natural and anthropogenic sources of element in the environment: regional geochemical surveys versus enrichment factors. *The Science of the total environment* 337, 91–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2004.06.011>
- US EPA, 2024. United States Environmental Protection Agency. Regional Screening Levels for Chemical Contaminants at Superfund Sites.
- US EPA, 2011. Exposure factors handbook. Office of research and Development, Washington, DC 20460, 2–6.
- US EPA, 1996. Soil screening guidance: Technical background document. EPA/540/R-95/128.
- US EPA, 1989. Risk Assessment Guidance for Superfund: pt. A. Human health evaluation manual. Office of Emergency and Remedial Response, US Environmental Protection Agency.

- Vos, H.C., Kanguuehi, K.I., Toesie, R., Eckardt, F.D., Ravenscroft, G., Fietz, S., 2024. Spatial variability of dust concentration and deposition around an industrial port in South Africa emphasises the complexity of sources and transport. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-024-01581-8>
- Wedepohl, K.H., 1995. The composition of the continental crust. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 59, 1217–1232. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037\(95\)00038-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037(95)00038-2)
- WHO, 2021. WHO global air quality guidelines: particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. World Health Organization.
- WHO, 2016. Ambient air pollution: a global assessment of exposure and burden of disease. World Health Organization, Geneva.
- Zheng, N., Hou, S., Wang, S., Sun, S., An, Q., Li, P., Li, X., 2020. Health risk assessment of heavy metals in street dust around a zinc smelting plant in China based on bioavailability and bioaccessibility. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 197, 110617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.110617>

8 Supplementary

Supplementary 1. The elements were analysed by the ICP-MS measurements and the associated abbreviations.

Na	Sodium	Cr	Chromium	Sr	Strontium
Mg	Magnesium	Mn	Manganese	Mo	Molybdenum
P	Phosphorus	Fe	Iron	Cd	Cadmium
K	Potassium	Co	Cobalt	Sn	Tin
Ca	Calcium	Ni	Nickel	Sb	Antimony
B	Boron	Cu	Copper	Ba	Barium
Al	Aluminium	Zn	Zinc	Hg	Mercury
Si	Silicon	As	Arsenic	Pb	Lead
V	Vanadium	Se	Selenium		

Supplementary 2. Recent sampling dates of the BSNE dust sampler.

Sampling date
13-11-2023
08-02-2024
22-04-2024
25-06-2024
30-07-2024
12-11-2024

Supplementary 3. The maximum daily and hourly PM_{2.5} concentration from the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) and the World Health Organisation (WHO).

	Current NAAQS standard	NAAQS standard in 2030	WHO standard
Daily average*	40 µg m ⁻³	20 µg m ⁻³	15 µg m ⁻³
Annual average	20 µg m ⁻³	15 µg m ⁻³	5 µg m ⁻³